

ISic0857

I.Sicily inscription 0857

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

"nel cimitero de' Cappucini"

Coordinates

37.078240, 15.295153

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, unknown

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Λεο[σ]θένης

2. Λέπιδος

3. καὶ Ἐράσμιος

4. ἔζησες ἔτ[η] κ

5. μῆν(ας) · δ · ἡμέρ(ας) η

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492485

EDCS 39102011

PHI 140334

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0040 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5403

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 49 n.244

Korhonen, K. 2007. Erudite forgeries or families seeking distinction? Cesare Gaetani's inscriptions from Syracuse. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 161: 291-298.

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0857. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4339702>